

SEA2SEE

RECIPE BOOK

SEASTAINABLE KITCHEN

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This recipe book is created as part of the European SEA2SEE project. It features delicious recipes made with seafood found in European waters or farmed within the European Union. Discover also an overview of the main challenges facing these resources and some practical seafood purchasing tips for responsible consumption.

SEA2SEE seeks to enhance consumer trust and acceptance of sustainably fished or farmed seafood in Europe. To achieve this, the project is developing and demonstrating an innovative end-to-end blockchain traceability model across the entire seafood value chain. Additionally, SEA2SEE is implementing societal and sectoral strategies aimed at co-creation, communication, and raising awareness of the benefits of consuming sustainable and nutritious seafood.

We invite you to discover the recipes, explore sustainability issues to make informed choices, and share your experience with family and friends. Bon appétit! Enjoy!

SEA2SEE Partners

FOOD HERITAGE

World Seafood Consumption

A Global Consumption That Keeps Growing

Global consumption of seafood (fishing and aquaculture) has doubled over the past 50 years, rising from 9.9 kg per capita per year in 1961 to 20.6 kg per capita per year in 2021, with Asia and Europe being the largest consumers of fish, crustaceans, mollusks and algae.

Cultural, economic, and geographical factors account for significant regional disparities, even within some countries, where annual per capita consumption can range from less than 1 kg to over 80 kg.

A Major Source of Protein Worldwide

For 3.2 billion people, aquatic products provide at least 20% of their animal protein intake. In 2021, seafood accounted for 15% of animal protein and 6% of total protein consumed globally.

SEAFOOD CONSUMPTION IN EUROPE

Europe: The World's Leading Seafood Buyer

Europe is the largest buyer of seafood globally (by value). Household spending on fisheries and aquaculture products in EU member states reaches around €140 per capita per year.

There is significant disparity in seafood consumption within Europe. Social changes in recent decades have altered eating habits: Europeans now consume fewer whole, unprocessed products and more prepared and ready-to-eat foods (such as smoked salmon, rillettes, pâtés, and surimi).

The most consumed species in Europe include tuna (all species combined), salmon, cod, Alaska pollock, shrimp (all species combined), and mussels.

The Most Traded Commodity in the World

European production amounts to approximately 4.05 million tonnes (fishing and aquaculture). However, demand exceeds supply, making imports a key component of the trade. Europeans are the world's largest importers of seafood.

The European Union imports seafood and aquaculture products from 150 different countries, totaling 8.87 million tonnes in 2021. The main exporters to the EU (by value) are China, Ecuador, and Morocco.

Additionally, the EU exports around 2.32 million tonnes of seafood, valued at €8.1 billion. The primary destination countries by volume are Norway, the United Kingdom, Nigeria, China, and the United States.

Key Exported and Imported Species

- **Exports (by value):** Salmonids, small pelagics (herring, mackerel, etc.), non-food products (fishmeal and fish oil), and demersal fish (cod, blue whiting, etc.).
- **Imports (by value):** Salmonids, crustaceans (shrimp, etc.), demersal fish (cod, Alaska pollock, etc.), and tuna species (skipjack and yellowfin).

Intra-EU Trade

Trade within the EU is also substantial, amounting to 6 million tons in 2022 (€27.4 billion). Salmonids and demersal fish are the most traded species between EU countries.

Processing

A portion of European-produced seafood is exported to China for processing (filleting, freezing, vacuum packaging, etc.) and then re-imported into Europe. While this reduces food industry labor costs, it imposes a significant environmental cost and raises social concerns.

**SEAFOOD CONSUMPTION
IN THE SEA2SEE PARTNERS'
COUNTRIES**

- PORTUGAL**
56.52 kg/capita/year
- SPAIN**
42.98 kg/capita/year
- FRANCE**
32.18 kg/capita/year
- GREECE**
19.56 kg/capita/year
- BULGARIA**
7.17 kg/capita/year

EU SUPPLY OF FISHERY AND AQUACULTURE PRODUCTS

→ In Europe, the majority of the seafood we consume is imported, whether from fishing or aquaculture, and some products travel thousands of kilometers before reaching our plates. Yet, European waters are home to fish, crustaceans, and mollusks that are often overlooked or underappreciated. Rediscovering these species not only helps to promote our marine resources but also reduces our carbon footprint. However, it is essential to ensure their sustainability by checking the state of resources and production practices (fishing or aquaculture) before making a purchase. This guide has been designed to help you with that.

**SEAFOOD CONSUMPTION
(kg/inhab./year) In Europe (EU 27)**

Portugal	56.52
Spain	42.98
France	32.18
Luxembourg	31.42
Italy	30.15
Cyprus	27.94
Latvia	24.47
Sweden	22.71
Croatia	22.12
Belgium	21.79
The Netherlands	21.08
Finland	20.63
Greece	19.56
Lithuania	17.80
Estonia	15.00
Ireland	14.56
Poland	14.26
Austria	12.67
Germany	12.51
Slovenia	11.71
Slovakia	10.32
Czechia	10.04
Romania	8.12
Bulgaria	7.17
Hungaria	6.55
EU average	23.71

Source Eumofa 2023

NATIONAL AND REGIONAL HIGHLIGHTS of the Sea2See partners' countries

PORTUGAL

Portugal is the EU's largest seafood consumer. Coastal regions, especially the north and central areas, lead in the consumption, especially enjoying sardines, octopus, and codfish. Lisbon and the Algarve also stand out for their seafood markets and iconic dishes, while inland areas consume less seafood, favoring meat-based dishes, though salted codfish remains a nationwide favorite. High demand for popular species puts significant pressure on fish stocks and marine ecosystems. It's crucial to diversify seafood consumption by choosing less common species and prioritizing those from sustainable sources, supporting healthier oceans, protecting the livelihoods of coastal communities, and maintaining Portugal's rich seafood heritage for future generations!

**SEAFOOD
CONSUMPTION**
56.5 kg
inhab/year

FRANCE

The French do not all have the same seafood consumption habits, which vary depending on where they live. Certain species are emblematic of specific regions, such as herring in the north, meagre in Charente, or salted cod in the Basque Country. In general, coastal regions—led by Brittany—are the largest consumers of seafood. The Grand Ouest (from Pays de la Loire to Normandy) accounts for a quarter of the nation's seafood consumption. In contrast, the Grand Est region consumes the least amount of fish. These disparities are rooted in different local traditions and cultures, which in coastal regions are naturally more oriented toward the sea.

**SEAFOOD
CONSUMPTION**
32 kg
inhab/year

**SEAFOOD
CONSUMPTION**
43 kg
inhab/year

SPAIN

Spain's coastal geography and rich maritime heritage make it a seafood enthusiast's dream, with an exceptional variety of dishes reflecting the diversity of the Mediterranean Sea, Atlantic Ocean, and Cantabrian Sea. Each region brings its own specialties: for instance, the Basque Country is known for bacalao al pil-pil (cod in a garlic sauce), Andalucía for its pescaito frito (fried seafood), Galicia for its celebrated shellfish (e.g scallops, barnacles, clams, cockles), and Catalonia for dishes like suquet de peix (fish stew) and its Palamós red prawns. The increasing demand for seafood, paired with the added pressures of climate change, are challenging the Spanish fishing industry to adopt more sustainable practices that prioritize responsible harvests, protect marine ecosystems, and ensure the long-term viability of fish populations. For instance, Galicia's efforts in sustainable shellfish harvesting ensure the preservation of species like mussels and scallops, while Catalonia promotes selective fishing to maintain biodiversity.

BULGARIA

Seafood consumption in Bulgaria varies significantly across regions, largely influenced by geography and cultural traditions. Coastal cities along the Black Sea, such as Varna and Burgas, exhibit the highest levels of seafood consumption, where fish like sprat, horse mackerel, black sea mullet and turbot are particularly popular, especially during the summer season. Other seafood species preferred by the population near the sea are rapa whelk (*Rapana venosa*) and mussels. The proximity to the sea does not only provide easy access to fresh seafood but also shapes local culinary practices.

Inland regions, such as those around Sofia or Plovdiv, tend to consume less seafood, with diets more heavily focused on meat and freshwater fish like carp, a staple during Christmas celebrations. The consumption of seafood inland often relies on frozen or imported options of marine products. These differences are deeply rooted in historical and cultural contexts. Coastal communities have longstanding fishing traditions that have embedded seafood into their regional cuisines, while landlocked areas have historically depended on farming and freshwater resources for protein. Additionally, economic factors influence consumption, with seafood being relatively expensive compared to other protein sources, especially in regions farther from the coast.

SEAFOOD CONSUMPTION

7 kg
inhab/year

SEAFOOD CONSUMPTION

19.6 kg
inhab/year

GREECE

Greece has a strong seafood tradition, influenced by its coastal geography and the Mediterranean diet. Greeks prefer fresh fish over frozen or processed options, with popular species including sea bream, sea bass, sardines, anchovies, and octopus.

Small-scale fisheries and a growing aquaculture sector, particularly for sea bass and sea bream, supply both local and export markets. Seafood consumption is seasonal and influenced by Orthodox fasting traditions, with high demand for octopus, squid, and shellfish. Traditional cooking methods, such as grilling and stewing, are widely used, and fish taverns play a key role in coastal communities. Despite its rich fisheries, Greece relies on seafood imports to meet demand. However, concerns over sustainability and overfishing are increasingly shaping consumption habits.

WHY DO TRACEABILITY AND SUSTAINABILITY MATTER?

Marine resources are not infinite

Today, we are increasingly aware of their fragility in the face of environmental changes and fishing pressures. The extraordinary natural ability of marine species to regenerate can be reduced—or even wiped out—by intensive fishing. Several marine species populations have already collapsed due to overexploitation (e.g., Newfoundland cod, Northeast Atlantic orange roughy).

Over the past 15 years, there has been significant mobilization within the European fishing industry to improve practices (in fishing and sourcing), supported by an ambitious reform of the European Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) focusing on environmental goals.

By 2020, all European fish stocks were supposed to be exploited at sustainable levels (CFP goal), and good ecological status of the marine environment was to be achieved (MSFD* goal). Unfortunately, these targets were not met, neither in the Atlantic nor in the Mediterranean.

- **In the North East Atlantic:** 30% of assessed stocks are still overfished, and the marine environment has yet to achieve good ecological status. While the proportion of overfished stocks has been slowly but steadily decreasing since the early 2000s, progress accelerated during 2020 and 2021 due to reduced fishing pressure linked to the COVID-19 crisis. However, in 2022, the percentage of overfished stocks slightly increased again.

- **In the Mediterranean and Black Sea:** Fishing pressure continues to decrease but remains extremely high—about double the maximum sustainable exploitation rate. Of the stocks assessed scientifically, 61% are overfished, and most stocks remain unassessed. This makes the Mediterranean and Black Sea among the most overfished areas in the world.

Global Challenges

Globally, significant issues persist: 37.7% of stocks are overexploited worldwide, highly destructive fishing techniques continue to impact ecosystems, and illegal fishing practices remain widespread. Much work is still needed to safeguard marine biodiversity, preserve resources, and ensure the sustainability of livelihoods dependent on these ecosystems.

Meanwhile, fish, mollusks, and crustaceans remain highly popular with consumers. Over the last three decades, their nutritional benefits have been widely and effectively promoted. Global production has grown from 40.5 million tons in the 1960s to nearly 185 million tons today.

Key Questions to Address

How can we meet the growing demand for high-quality aquatic protein while preserving marine wildlife and encouraging sustainable practices? Which species should we prioritize?

EAT WISE, CHOOSE RIGHT: TIPS FOR RESPONSIBLE SEAFOOD CONSUMPTION

Understanding seafood's origin and production methods is crucial for protecting marine ecosystems.

Make sure the scientific name is provided to check the species you buy

The same common name can hide several species whose stocks are in different conditions.

Take origin into account

Check the origin and the sustainability of the population to avoid to buy species that are overfished.

Take size into account

Check the maturity size which is often bigger than the commercial size (some animals are caught before they can reproduce).

Look for the production method

Caught or Farmed, consider the impacts of the fishing gears or the production methods have on the environment. Choose the less harmful option.

Additionally, look for labels and eco-certifications such as:

The sustainability data regarding the preferred fishing areas for each species is valid for the year 2025 but may evolve based on the status of fish populations and fisheries management.

For up-to-date information, refer to the Ethic Ocean mobile app (free access).

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PREPARATION: 15' | COOKING: 45' | PORTIONS: 4

EUROPEAN BARRACUDA BRANDADE

with Sweet Potato Purée and Tempura Spinach Leaves

Cook: Chef Quim Casellas, Casamar restaurant in Llafranc, Spain.

Species: European barracuda (*Sphyraena sphyraena*).

INGREDIENTS

For the brandade

- 500 g European barracuda, skinned and deboned
- 300 ml olive oil
- 4 garlic cloves

For the sweet potato purée

- 1 sweet potato
- Salt and pepper
- Butter

For the crispy spinach leaves

- 12 large spinach leaves
- 30 g baking powder
- 180 g wheat flour
- Salt
- Mineral water

METHOD

In a pot, add a drizzle of olive oil and sauté the peeled and sliced garlic. Shred the European barracuda and drain it well.

Add it to the pot with the garlic and cook gently.

Once the barracuda is tender, place it in a blender or food processor and mix at high speed. Gradually add olive oil to emulsify and thicken. Adjust seasoning with salt and set aside.

Separately, season the unpeeled sweet potato with salt, wrap it in aluminum foil, and bake it for 35 minutes at 185°C. Once soft (test by poking with a skewer), peel it. Use a blender or mash it manually with some butter to make the purée.

For the tempura, mix the flour, baking powder, water, and salt until you achieve a smooth, creamy texture. Chill the batter in the refrigerator to cool. It's very important to clean and dry the spinach leaves thoroughly. Once the tempura is chilled, dip the leaves in the batter and fry them in hot oil until they become crispy. Let them drain on paper towels to remove excess oil.

To serve, place a small amount of European barracuda brandade in the center of the plate, top with a little sweet potato purée, and finish with the crispy spinach leaves. You can serve them as dips to scoop the brandade.

Flavors with a Story Quim Casellas is known for his exceptional ability to blend tradition and innovation. His cuisine tells stories using locally sourced ingredients, creating a harmonious dialogue between the sea and the land. Each dish reflects his deep connection to the territory and its people, showcasing local producers and their craftsmanship. He actively champions sustainable seafood and honors the efforts of local fishermen. Casellas's cooking is more than food - it's a tribute to his roots and a celebration of Mediterranean culture, balancing authenticity and creativity in every bite.

The European barracuda (espet in Catalan) (*Sphyraena sphyraena*), is not your typical fish to feature in a recipe book, but that makes it so exciting! This sleek, silvery-blue predator is a member of the bluefish family. Typically a pelagic species, it roams the upper layers of the water column up to 100 meters deep, although smaller individuals are often found closer to the seafloor. This species of barracuda are social creatures, forming schools ranging from ten to over two hundred fish. Their diet? Mostly other fish, but they'll happily snack on cephalopods and crustaceans. Due to the lack of scientific data on its stock status, it is recommended to consume it in moderation. Prefer line-caught barracuda over 28 cm in size. In this recipe, we're bringing the espet into the spotlight—not only for its unique flavor but also to show how this lesser-known species can shine in a dish. By turning it into a flavorful brandade, we're demonstrating how blue fish can be just as versatile and delicious as their more popular counterparts. Plus, choosing a fish like this one, we are also supporting sustainable practices and the Blue Economy.

PREPARATION: 15' | COOKING: 40' | PORTIONS: 4

BONITO CASSEROLE "MARMITA DE BONITO"

Cook: Carlos Mazorra de Quero (anonymous daily cook) at his home, Santander, Spain.

Species: Atlantic Bonito (*Sarda sarda*).

INGREDIENTS

- 600 g fresh tuna (bonito), cut into cubes
- 4 medium potatoes, peeled and "cracked" into irregular pieces (Put part of the knife in and then lever the knife to "crack" a piece off the potato. This gives irregular edges that will contribute to give texture to the dish. See the dish picture to get an idea of size)
- 1 large onion, chopped
- 1 red bell pepper, chopped
- 1 green bell pepper, chopped
- 4 tomatoes, peeled and chopped
- 4 cloves garlic, minced
- 1 bay leaf
- 1.5 teaspoons sweet paprika
- 600 ml fish broth (or water)
- 5 tablespoons olive oil
- Salt and pepper to taste

" I am sure there is a version of this dish in every fishing village around the world (different fish, same idea). This one is typical from Northern Spain, and uses the basic ingredients found in a fishing boat going out to sea for the annual bonito summer "hunt". We cook this for family and friends reunions every summer. "

METHOD

In a large pot, heat the olive oil over medium heat. Add the onions, bell peppers, and garlic, sautéing until softened (about 5 minutes).

Add the tomatoes, paprika, cooking until the tomatoes soften, about 10 minutes.

Add the "cracked" potatoes, bay leaf and fish broth. Season with salt and pepper. Cover and simmer for 20 minutes or until the potatoes are tender.

Add the cubed tuna, gently mixing it into the stew. You can turn off the fire and cook with the residual heat until the tuna is just cooked through.

Taste and adjust salt and pepper as needed.

PRESENTATION

Serve in bowls, paired with crusty bread to enjoy with the sauce.

The Atlantic bonito (*Sarda sarda*) is a migratory fish with a streamlined body and a blue-grey coloration on its upper side, contrasting with a silvery belly. It is found in the waters of the Eastern Atlantic, the Mediterranean, and the Black Sea. In spring and summer, it migrates in large schools, following warm currents along the coastlines, particularly in the Mediterranean. The bonito is highly prized for its fast swimming and its firm, flavorful flesh. Due to limited scientific data on its stock status, it is advised to consume it in moderation. When possible, choose line-caught bonito.

PREPARATION: 15' | COOKING: 50' | PORTIONS: 4

COD WITH TOMATO

Cook: Carlos Mazorra de Quero (anonymous daily cook) at his home, Santander, Spain.

Species: Cod (*Gadus morhua*).

INGREDIENTS

- 4 cod fillets (desalted)
- 800 g crushed tomatoes (fresh or canned)
- 1 onion
- 3 garlic cloves
- 1 green pepper
- 1 red pepper
- Extra virgin olive oil
- Salt
- Herbes de Provence (optional)
- Good sweet paprika ("Pimentón de la Vera dulce")
- Bicarbonate (1/2 teaspoon, to adjust the acidity of the tomatoes)
- Flour and eggs

METHOD

TOMATO SAUCE

In a thick based deep pan, add three table spoons of olive oil and sauté the finely chopped onion with the sliced garlic. Add a couple of pinches of salt.

When the onion becomes translucent, add the green bell pepper and the red bell pepper cut into strips. Cook over medium heat until the peppers are tender

Add a teaspoon of good sweet paprika now if you have it.

Add the crushed tomatoes and herbes de Provence. Cook on a medium/low heat for about 20-30 minutes, stirring occasionally.

Adjust the acidity of the tomatoes with a pinch of bicarbonate and correct with salt to taste.

COD

Meanwhile, cut each cod fillet in two or three pieces.

Prepare a plate with some flour and a second plate with beaten egg.

Heat plenty olive oil in a skillet, enough to have a couple of centimetres deep.

Lightly coat the cod fillets in flour, pat off any excess, and soak them in the egg.

Fry the cod over medium heat for about 1 minute on each side, until the coating is sealed. Take them out on to a plate (they will let go of some liquid that we will incorporate to the sauce).

Place the cod pieces carefully on the tomato sauce (including the liquid that might have come out of them) and let them cook, low heat, for 5-10 minutes, until the cod is fully cooked and has absorbed the flavours of the sauce.

Gently shake the skillet occasionally to ensure the sauce embraces the cod.

Cod with tomato can be served with white rice, or better still with a good thick slice of bread for the sauce.

The Atlantic cod (*Gadus morhua*) is a demersal fish that lives close to the seabed, typically found from the coast down to depths of 600 meters in the North Atlantic, ranging from Canadian waters to the Barents Sea. It is most commonly concentrated between 150 and 200 meters deep. With a robust, elongated body and a pale, silvery belly, it has a characteristic dark green or brownish back. Cod plays a significant role in commercial fishing but has faced dramatic declines in population due to overfishing. Due to concerns about its stock status, it is advisable to consume cod with caution and opt for sustainably sourced or certified options to ensure its long-term preservation.

PREPARATION: 15' | COOKING: 15' | PORTIONS: 4

HAKE TARTARE WITH A WAKAMÉ HEART

Cook: Gurvan Le Meur, France.

Recipe presented at the Olivier Roellinger European culinary contest, *for the preservation of marine resources* (1st price, 2023).

Species: European hake (*Merluccius merluccius*).

INGREDIENTS

- 200 g hake fillet
- 60 g wakame seaweed
- 225 g carrots
- 6 cl olive oil
- 5 passion fruits
- Salt
- Pepper

METHOD

HAKE TARTARE

Cut the hake fillet into thin, even strips, then dice them into small, uniform cubes of about 5 mm. Finely chop the wakame seaweed and prepare a brunoise of carrots. Mix the hake, wakame, and carrot brunoise together.

VINAIGRETTE

Separate the seeds from the juice of 3 to 5 passion fruits. Set the seeds aside for presentation. Incorporate the juice into the olive oil, season with salt and pepper. Add the vinaigrette to the tartare mixture.

PLATING

The tartare can be shaped into a round mold, but feel free to get creative with the presentation. Garnish with the reserved passion fruit seeds.

European hake is easily recognizable by its elongated body, large mouth lined with long, pointed teeth, and two dorsal fins. It inhabits waters from coastal areas down to 1,000 meters deep in the Northeast Atlantic, Mediterranean, and Black Sea. It is best to choose line-caught hake with a minimum size of 57 cm (Atlantic) or 28 cm (Mediterranean).

Preferably choose European hake from the Northeast Atlantic (avoid Mediterranean hake).

PREPARATION: 15' | COOKING: 15' | PORTIONS: 4

TRADITIONAL GREEK MONKFISH SOUP

with lemon, tarragon, and saffron

Cook: Nikolaos Agrafiotits, Greece.

Recipe presented at the Olivier Roellinger European culinary contest, *for the preservation of marine resources* (3rd price, 2019).

Species: Monkfish (Common monkfish *Lophius piscatorius* or Blackbellied monkfish *Lophius budegassa*).

INGREDIENTS

- 1 kg of monkfish
- 300 g of potatoes
- 300 g of carrots
- 200 g of onions
- 200 g of celery
- 2 lemons
- 1 bunch of tarragon
- 1 g of red saffron
- Olive oil

METHOD

FISH

Clean the fish. Remove the skin and fillet it.

Place the bones and skin in a small pot with cold water and bring to a boil. Skim the broth, then let it simmer for 15 minutes.

SOUP

Clean, peel, and dice the vegetables into small cubes.

Set aside. In a pan, sauté the vegetables in olive oil.

Cover with the fish broth and add the saffron.

Simmer for 10 minutes over low heat.

Once the vegetables are tender, add the monkfish fillets cut into large chunks. Let simmer gently for 5 minutes.

Season with salt, pepper, and lemon juice.

Before serving, sprinkle with tarragon and serve hot.

The monkfish, also known as anglerfish, inhabits depths ranging from 100 to 1,000 meters. A poor swimmer, it remains discreet and attracts its prey using its fishing filament. *Lophius piscatorius* is one of the two anglerfish species found in the Atlantic, along with *Lophius budegassa*. These species are not endangered, unlike the Chinese anglerfish (*Lophius litulon*), whose larger individuals are becoming increasingly rare.

PREPARATION: 15' | COOKING: 15' | PORTIONS: 4

POACHED CARP FILLETS

squash fries, green apple salad, and mayonnaise

Cook: Martin Pacsai, Hungary.

Recipe presented at the Olivier Roellinger European culinary contest, *for the preservation of marine resources* (1st price, 2019).

Species: Common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*).

INGREDIENTS

- 600 g of common carp
- 500 g of celery
- 500 g of squash
- 100 g of lemon
- 500 g of green apples
- 100 g of orange
- 100 g of lime
- 1 egg yolk
- 100 g of breadcrumbs
- 2 g of salt
- 2 g of sugar
- 30 cl of olive oil
- 20 cl of sunflower oil
- Lobster broth

METHOD

GARNISH

Dice the celery and green apples into small cubes. Marinate them with olive oil, salt, and sugar. Prepare an emulsified sauce with the egg yolk, breadcrumbs, olive oil, and the juice of the lemon, orange, and lime.

Cut the squash into sticks and fry them in sunflower oil. Set aside.

FISH PREPARATION

Fillet and debone the carp. Poach the fillets in the lobster broth. Keep warm.

PLATING

Arrange the warm carp fillets harmoniously with the celery-apple salad, cooked squash, and citrus sauce. Sprinkle with freshly chopped parsley before serving.

The common carp has a thick body covered in scales. It has a dark green or bronze coloration on its back, with a lighter shade on its belly. It is the most well-known freshwater species in Europe and one of the main farmed species worldwide. Check the production conditions for farmed carp.

PREPARATION: 15' | COOKING: 15' | PORTIONS: 4

SMOKED HORSE MACKEREL

Flemish-style asparagus, and mashed potatoes

Cook: Michael Angelo Van Liere, Belgium.
Recipe presented at the Olivier Roellinger European culinary contest, *for the preservation of marine resources* (2nd price, 2022).

Species: Horse mackerel (*Trachurus trachurus*).

INGREDIENTS

- 600 g of horse mackerel fillets
- 750 g of white asparagus
- 400 g of Bintje potatoes
- 20 g of flat-leaf parsley
- 1 yellow lemon
- 7 eggs
- 125 g of unsalted butter
- 20 g of sherry vinegar
- 5 g of nutmeg
- 10 g of white pepper
- 20 g of strong Dijon mustard
- 50 g of brown sugar
- Fine or coarse salt

METHOD

MASHED POTATOES

Peel, cut, and cook the potatoes in salted water. Once cooked, drain and mash them using a Food mill. Add 25 g of butter, salt, pepper, nutmeg, and mustard.

FISH

In a saucepan, mix the sherry vinegar and brown sugar. Bring to a boil and let it reduce for 2 to 3 minutes.

Cover the fillets with coarse or fine salt for 30 minutes, then rinse and pat them dry.

Preheat the smoker. Once hot, place the fillets inside for 5 minutes.

Remove from the smoker and coat with the sherry vinegar and brown sugar mixture.

EGGS

Hard-boil the eggs. Separate the whites from the yolks, chop them separately, then mix them together. Season with salt, pepper, nutmeg, and lemon juice. Add 75 g of melted butter and the chopped parsley.

ASPARAGUS

Peel the asparagus and cook them in salted water with 10 g of butter for 6 to 7 minutes, monitoring the cooking process. Lightly grill them.

PLATING

Place the grilled asparagus at the center of the plate with the mashed potatoes beside them. Arrange the smoked fish fillets on top of the asparagus, avoiding the heads. Add the egg mixture over the mashed potatoes. Finish with some lemon zest on top of the eggs. Serve hot.

The Atlantic horse mackerel (*Trachurus trachurus*) has a fusiform, elongated body with a deeply notched tail fin. Its lateral line is curved, and the posterior part of the line features bony scutes. A distinctive black spot is visible near the gill covers. This migratory species is found in the waters of the Eastern Atlantic, the Mediterranean, and the Black Sea. Horse mackerels are typically seen in large schools, swimming actively near the surface or in mid-water. Given its important role in marine ecosystems and its high commercial value, it is recommended to choose horse mackerel that are at least 27 cm long and are from sustainable populations.

PREPARATION: 15' | COOKING: 15' | PORTIONS: 4

CONGER BLANQUETTE

with glazed vegetables

Cook: Antoine Moal, France.

Recipe presented at the Olivier Roellinger european culinary contest, *for the preservation of marine resources* (3rd price, 2018).

Species: Conger (*Conger conger*).

INGREDIENTS

- | | |
|------------------------|------------------------|
| - 1 kg of conger | - 10 cl of cream |
| - 250 g of fish bones | - 150 g of butter |
| - 300 g of carrots | - 1 egg yolk |
| - 20 g of shallots | - 30 g of flour |
| - 250 g of rutabaga | - 30 g of caster sugar |
| - 1 bouquet garni | - Mushrooms |
| - 10 g of lemon | - Salt |
| - 40 g of large onions | - Pepper |

METHOD

VEGETABLES

Peel and wash the vegetables.

Cut the carrots and rutabagas into pieces. Sauté the mushrooms in butter. Set aside.

CONGER

Skin, trim, fillet, and debone the fish. Soak the bones in water to remove impurities. Keep refrigerated.

Make the fish stock: In a sauté pan, sweat a chopped onion, add the fish bones, and cover halfway with water.

Cook for 50 minutes with the bouquet garni. Let cool.

Cook the conger and make the sauce: Cut the conger fillets into 50 g pieces, sear them in butter in a sauté pan with chopped shallots, then add the cold fish stock until just covered. Bring to a boil, then remove the fish pieces.

SAUCE

Make the velouté sauce (Roux: 50 g butter, 50 g flour, 1 liter of fish stock).

Add the hot fish stock to the cold roux, bring to a boil.

Add the cream, and at the last moment, thicken with an egg yolk and add lemon juice. The sauce should no longer boil.

Once the blanquette sauce is ready, add the conger pieces back in.

PLATING

In warm deep plates, place the conger pieces and add the hot vegetables. Coat everything with the sauce.

The conger has a long, snake-like body and inhabits rocky seabeds between 0 and 300 meters deep in the Atlantic, the Mediterranean, and the Black Sea.

It hides in rocks, crevices, and shipwrecks during the day and emerges at night to hunt.

Its biological characteristics are still poorly understood, so it should be consumed in moderation.

With the right technique to remove its numerous bones, its firm flesh is highly appreciated by connoisseurs.

PREPARATION: 15' | COOKING: 45' | PORTIONS: 6

FISH TERRINE WITH SAIthe AND/OR HADDOCK

Species: Haddock (*Melanogrammus aeglefinus*) or Saithe (*Pollachius virens*).

INGREDIENTS

- 500 g (1 lb) sustainable fish fillets (e.g., saithe and haddock, boneless)
- 3 eggs
- 100 g (3.5 oz) heavy cream or crème fraîche
- 1 shallot, finely chopped
- 1 garlic clove, minced
- 1 small bunch of parsley (about 10 g), chopped
- 50 g (1.7 oz) breadcrumbs
- 1 tbsp olive oil
- Salt and pepper, to taste
- Juice of half a lemon

FOR SERVING

- Light mayonnaise or a lemon yogurt sauce
- A fresh, crunchy green salad

METHOD

FISH

Rinse and pat the fish fillets dry. Cut them into pieces and place them in a food processor. Pulse until finely chopped but not fully puréed to retain some texture.

PREPARE THE MIXTURE

In a large mixing bowl, whisk together the eggs and cream. Add the shallot, garlic, parsley, and breadcrumbs. Mix well. Fold in the chopped fish and stir until the mixture is smooth and even. Season with salt, pepper, and lemon juice.

COOKING

Preheat the oven to 180°C (350°F). Grease a loaf tin with olive oil and pour the mixture into the tin. Bake for 40 to 45 minutes, or until the fish loaf is firm and golden on top. A knife inserted in the center should come out clean.

COOLING

Let the loaf cool to room temperature before removing it from the tin. This dish can be served warm, at room temperature, or chilled.

PRESENTATION

Serve the fish loaf in thick slices with homemade dill mayonnaise or a tangy yogurt-lemon sauce. Pair it with a mâche or arugula salad for a light and balanced meal.

The haddock (*Melanogrammus aeglefinus*) has a fusiform body with a silver-grey back, a white belly, and a dark spot below its lateral line. It features a small barb on its lower jaw. This demersal species is found near rocky, gravelly, or sandy seabeds at depths between 40 and 300 meters in the North-East Atlantic, from Iceland and northern Norway to the Bay of Biscay, and in the North-West Atlantic. Preferably choose haddock over 46 cm in size from sustainable populations.

HERRING PICKLED IN ROSE BEETROOTS

with potato, plankton buttermilk & apple

Cook: Marcin Popielarz, Poland.

Recipe presented at the Olivier Roellinger European culinary contest, *For the preservation of marine resources* (2019).

Species: Herring (*Clupea harengus*).

INGREDIENTS

- 600 g herring (salted)
- 300 g Reinette apples
- 150 g Chioggia beetroots
- 120 g dill
- 25 g garlic
- 200 g onion
- 400 g potatoes
- 150 ml olive oil pomace
- 125 ml buttermilk
- 500 ml sunflower oil
- 100 g unsalted butter
- 250 ml low-fat cream
- 200 ml thin-fat cream
- 500 ml semi-skimmed milk
- 1 egg
- 10 g Dijon mustard
- 3 g bay leaves
- 275 g caster sugar
- 175 ml cider vinegar
- 175 ml white wine vinegar

METHOD

PICKLING THE HERRING IN CHIOGGIA BEETROOT AND VINEGAR MARINADE

Thinly slice the Chioggia beetroots. In a saucepan, simmer white wine vinegar, cider vinegar, 150g caster sugar, bay leaves, sliced garlic, and half the dill until the sugar dissolves. Let cool slightly. Submerge herring fillets in the marinade and refrigerate for 24 hours.

MASHED POTATO WITH BUTTER AND CREAM

Peel and cut potatoes into chunks. Boil in salted water until tender. Drain and mash while hot. Incorporate 100g unsalted butter, 250ml low-fat cream, and 200ml thin-fat cream until smooth. Season with salt and keep warm.

VINEGAR-BLANCHED ONIONS

Thinly slice onions. Bring 100ml white wine vinegar and 50g caster sugar to a boil. Blanch onions for 10-15 seconds, then cool.

WHITE ENDIVE

Trim and separate the inner leaves. Brush lightly with olive oil and season with salt. Keep refrigerated.

DILL AND PLANKTON OIL

Blend 500ml sunflower oil, 50g dill, and plankton (if available). Strain through a sieve. Store in a bottle for drizzling.

PICKLED DILL & COMPRESSED APPLE IN PLANKTON OIL

Store fresh dill tips in ice water. Thinly slice Reinette apple and vacuum-seal with plankton and dill oil. Alternatively, marinate for 30 minutes.

RANCH SAUCE (MAYONNAISE, CRÈME FRAÎCHE & BUTTERMILK)

Whisk together mayonnaise, 100ml crème fraîche, and 125ml buttermilk. Add 10g Dijon mustard. Season with salt and refrigerate.

SIMPLY DRESSING FOR FINISHING

Mix olive oil, a few drops of vinegar, and salt for a light dressing. Use to dress the vegetables.

PLATING & PRESENTATION

Arrange pickled herring in a curved shape. Spoon mashed potatoes and garnish with compressed apple and fresh dill. Add vinegar-blanched onions and place white endive for height. Swirl ranch sauce on the plate, drizzle with dill and plankton oil, and finish with simply dressing.

PREPARATION: 30' | COOKING: 10' | PORTIONS: 4

FAKE MEAGRE CEVICHE

Cook: Carlos Alberto Espinal.

Species: Meagre (*Argyrosomus Regius*).

INGREDIENTS

- 700 g of meagre fillets (1,3 to 1,5 kg of fish)
- 2 red onions
- 4 celery stalks
- A bunch of coriander
- 4 passion fruits
- 1 large orange
- 2 large lemons
- Olive oil
- Salt and pepper
- Fresh hot pepper or pepperoncini (to taste)

This refreshing and tangy dish is called **"Fake Ceviche"** because it does not use raw fish. Instead, the dish features diced, skin-on corvina fillets. The pan-fried, crispy corvina skin contrasts the refreshing ceviche-like flavours for a dish that works well in both winter and summer.

1

FILLET THE CORVINA

Trim the fillet and carefully slice along both sides of the lateral line to remove the pin bones. Cut the fillet into 4 cm x 4 cm squares, keeping the skin on. Set aside.

2

PREPARE THE VEGETABLES

- Thinly slice the red onions into julienne strips.
- Slice the celery stalks into thin sheets or cubes.
- Roughly chop the coriander leaves.

3

PREPARE THE "LECHE DE TIGRE" (Citrus marinade):

- Scoop the passion fruit pulp into a sieve. Press the pulp with a spoon to extract the juice, discarding the seeds.
- Squeeze the orange and lemon juice, and combine with the passion fruit juice.
- Finely chop the hot pepper or pepperoncini and add to the juice mixture, adjusting the amount to your preferred spice level.

- Add salt and pepper to taste.
- Drizzle a small amount of olive oil into the mixture.
- Add the sliced onions, celery, and coriander to the juice mixture.
- Let the mixture stand for 15-20 minutes.

4

COOK THE MEAGRE

- Heat a pan or plancha (griddle) over high heat. Grease with olive oil.
- Place the meagre squares, skin-side down. Cook without flipping until the skin turns crispy. If you prefer a rare fillet finish, use high heat and fast sear for about 3-5 minutes. If you prefer medium or well-done, lower the heat and let the fish cook for about 7-10 minutes.

5

SERVE

- Once the meagre is ready, transfer the squares to a serving platter.
- Spoon a generous amount of Leche de Tigre over each square of meagre.
- Serve at once, accompanied by crackers, or a rusk bread, like Greek dakos or Italian friselle.

ROASTED LINE-CAUGHT MEAGRE

with seaweed, citrus risotto, and lemon sauce

Cook: Florian Pereira, France.

Recipe presented at the Olivier Roellinger European culinary contest, *for the preservation of marine resources* (3rd price, 2021).

Species: Meagre (*Argyrosomus regius*).

INGREDIENTS

- 600 g or 4 meagre steaks (line-caught)
- 400 g of cleaned cockles
- 2 dried nori seaweed sheets
- 1.5 L of fish stock
- 250 g of Arborio rice
- 50 g of green olives
- 100 g of onions
- 2 yellow lemons
- 2 limes
- ½ bunch of lemongrass
- ½ bunch of basil
- 50 g of fennel
- 100 g of Parmesan cheese
- 125 g of Bordier seaweed butter
- 20 ml of Ricard or another anise-flavored aperitif
- 200 ml of white wine
- Salt
- Pepper

METHOD

FISH

Keep the meagre steaks chilled until ready to cook.

RISOTTO

Sweat the chopped onions in olive oil, add the rice and stir until slightly translucent. Deglaze with white wine and let it reduce. Gradually add 1.35 L of fish stock while stirring, cooking for about 14 minutes.

SAUCE

Flambé the Ricard in a saucepan, then add the remaining 150 ml of fish stock. Infuse with lemongrass, reduce, and whisk in 75 g of butter and 75 g of seaweed butter. Add the juice of one yellow lemon and adjust seasoning.

SEAFOOD COOKING

Sear the meagre steaks in foaming 75 g of seaweed butter for 2-3 minutes. Zest one lime over the fillets. Sweat the chopped shallots, add the cockles, and deglaze with white wine. Finish the risotto by stirring in the Parmesan (reserve a few shavings for plating) and 75 g of butter. Segment one lime and one yellow lemon, keeping only the citrus supremes. Add the citrus supremes, chopped olives, and finely chopped basil to the risotto.

PLATING

Place the risotto at the center of the plate and arrange the meagre steak on top. Sprinkle the finely chopped nori over the fish skin and arrange the cockles around it. Use a mandoline to slice fennel thinly for added height, along with Parmesan shavings. Emulsify the sauce and pour it over the dish while hot.

The meagre is a migratory fish with an elongated, silver-colored body, darker on the back. It inhabits the waters of the Eastern Atlantic, the Mediterranean, and the Black Sea. In France, during spring, it swims up the Gironde estuary to reproduce. Due to the lack of scientific data on its stock status, it should be consumed in moderation. Prefer line-caught meagre size or sustainably farm raised meagre.

ROASTED SAITHE on creamy polenta with Dubarry foam

Cook: Natacha Morin, France.

Recipe presented at the Olivier Roellinger European culinary contest, *for the preservation of marine resources* (4th price, 2012).

Species: Saithe (*Pollachius virens*).

INGREDIENTS

- 800 g of saithe fillet (with skin)
- ½ cauliflower
- A few sprigs of chervil
- 120 g of fine polenta semolina
- 0.8 L of heavy cream
- 0.7 L of milk
- 40 g of unsalted butter
- Olive oil
- White pepper
- Salt, coarse salt, and Guérande fleur de sel

METHOD

VEGETABLES & POLENTA

Bring the milk, heavy cream, and butter to a boil. Gradually pour in the polenta while stirring. Cook on low heat for a few minutes, stirring constantly. Season to taste and keep warm.

FISH

Ensure the fillets are free of bones. Cut the fillets into 4 equal portions. Place them on a baking tray (Flesh side down), season, and brush with a little olive oil. Bake in the oven at 120°C for 10 minutes.

SAUCE

Cauliflower foam (Mousse Dubarry): Remove the leaves and cut the cauliflower into florets. Cook the cauliflower gently in a saucepan with heavy cream, avoiding boiling. Season. Blend the cauliflower with the cream until smooth. Strain through a fine sieve to remove any small pieces. Pour the liquid into a siphon, close it, and keep warm in a bain-marie. Charge the siphon with gas.

PLATING

Using a ring mold, plate the polenta. Place the saithe fillet on top. Cover with the Dubarry foam. Sprinkle with Guérande fleur de sel and garnish with chervil sprigs. Finish with a drizzle of olive oil.

Saithe (*Pollachius virens*) has an elongated, laterally compressed body with a pointed head and a slightly protruding lower jaw. Its lateral line is light-colored and straight. This species can be found in the waters of the North Atlantic, from the coast to depths of 200 meters. It lives in midwater or close to the seabed, where it hunts for prey. Saithe is often confused with cod but can be distinguished by its appearance and habitat preferences. Preferably choose saithe over 55 cm in size, caught by line, from sustainable populations.

PREPARATION: 15' | COOKING: 15' | PORTIONS: 4

HERB-CRUSTED WHITING

with lemon and mashed potatoes

Species: Whiting (*Merlangius merlangus*).

INGREDIENTS

- 4 whiting fillets
- 2 tablespoons breadcrumbs
- 2 tablespoons fresh parsley, chopped
- 2 tablespoons chives, chopped
- 2 garlic cloves, minced
- 1 lemon (zest + juice)
- 4 tablespoons olive oil
- Salt, pepper
- 800 g potatoes
- 20 cl milk
- 40 g butter
- Salt, pepper

METHOD

MASHED POTATOES

Peel and cut the potatoes into chunks. Boil them in a pot of salted water for about 15 minutes until tender. Drain, then mash with the butter and warm milk. Season with salt and pepper.

HERB CRUST

In a bowl, mix the breadcrumbs, parsley, chives, minced garlic, lemon zest, salt, and pepper.

WHITING

Preheat the oven to 200°C (390°F). Place the whiting fillets on a baking sheet lined with parchment paper. Drizzle with olive oil and lemon juice. Spread the herb crust evenly over the fillets. Bake for 10 to 12 minutes until golden and cooked through.

SERVE

Plate the golden whiting fillets alongside the creamy mashed potatoes. Drizzle with extra lemon juice and serve with a fresh green salad or roasted vegetables.

The whiting (*Merlangius merlangus*) has an elongated body with a prominent upper jaw, a black spot at the base of the pectoral fin, and a dark lateral line. This demersal species lives near the seafloor, typically found in gravelly or muddy bottoms at depths ranging from 10 to 200 meters. It is found in the waters of the North-East Atlantic (from northern Norway to Portugal), the Mediterranean, and the Black Sea. Preferably choose whiting over 25 cm in size, caught by line, from sustainable populations.

PREPARATION: 15' | COOKING: 15' | PORTIONS: 4

MEUNIÈRE-STYLE MULLET WITH CONDIMENTS

Cook: Sébastien Delorme, France.

Recipe presented at the Olivier Roellinger European culinary contest, *for the preservation of marine resources* (2nd price, 2023).

Species: Black mullet (*Chelon labrosus*).

INGREDIENTS

- 800 g of black mullet fillets
- ½ cauliflower
- 500 g of pak choi
- 40 cl of fresh cream
- 150 g of butter
- 100 g of flour
- 2 limes
- ¼ bunch of parsley
- 50 g of pine nuts
- 2 cl of olive oil
- Salt
- Pepper

METHOD

FISH

Coat the fillets in flour on both sides.
Sear them in a pan with the remaining butter until golden brown.
Baste generously with the butter while cooking.

CAULIFLOWER CREAM

Cut the cauliflower into pieces and cook it in the cream for about 20 minutes until a knife can easily pierce it.
Season with salt and pepper.
Blend the cauliflower until smooth and creamy. Keep warm.

GARNISH

Blanch the pak choi leaves in salted water for 1 minute.
Before plating, sear them in a pan with olive oil, then season with salt and pepper.

SAUCE

Prepare a browned butter (beurre noisette) with 100 g of butter.
Remove from heat and add lightly toasted pine nuts, lime segments, and chopped parsley.

PLATING

Spread a layer of cauliflower cream on the plate.
Add the pak choi.
Place the fish fillet on top, then pour the sauce over the fish.

Several species of mullet, also called «mugil» exist: the black mullet (*Chelon labrosus*), golden mullet (*Liza aurata*), flathead mullet (*Mugil cephalus*), and thinlip mullet (*Liza ramada*). In spring, these fish migrate in schools to estuaries, lagoons, and rivers to feed on small worms, algae, and crustaceans, before returning to the sea to spawn. Though relatively unknown to consumers, mullet is a sustainable alternative to overexploited species. However, due to limited scientific data on its population, it should be consumed in moderation.

PREPARATION: 20' | COOKING: 25' | PORTIONS: 4

SEABASS WITH NOTCHWEEDS AND OUZO IN THE POT

Cook: Nena Ismirnoglou.

Dishes from "The concrete project" company

Species: Seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*).

INGREDIENTS

- 1 kg of seabass fillets, seasoned with salt and pepper
- 1,200 gr. (weighed gross) notchweeds cleaned
(Separate the leaves from the tender stalks)
Leave the leaves whole, while finely chop the tender stalks)
- 1 large dry onion, diced
- 1 bunch mint, chopped
- 60 ml lemon juice
- 60 ml of ouzo
- 70 ml olive oil
- salt, freshly ground pepper

METHOD

To make seabass with notchweeds and ouzo in the pot, start by heating the oil in a wide pot over high heat and sauté the fish for about 1-2 minutes on each side, until golden brown.

Transfer them with a slotted spoon to a plate.

In the same pot and in the same oil, sauté the onions together with the chopped stalks from the onion for about 4-5 minutes, until they soften.

Pour the leaves from the burdock root, mint, salt, freshly ground pepper and 38 about 100 ml of water and cook for about 6-7 minutes, until they soften slightly.

Place carefully on top of the greens and fish, season with salt and pepper, pour in the ouzo and lemon juice and cook for about another 7-8 minutes, until the fish is done, and the aromas and flavors have mixed.

Remove from heat and serve immediately.

The European sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) has an elongated body with a grey back and white belly, with a lower jaw longer than the upper jaw. It is a coastal demersal species that lives near sandy or rocky seabeds, and can also thrive in brackish waters. Fishing: check the sustainability of the fishing zone before buying wild sea bass. Preferably choose line-caught individuals over 42 cm (Gulf of Biscay), 37 cm (Gulf of Lion), or 45 cm (other regions).
Farm raised: Check the production conditions.

PREPARATION: 15' | COOKING: 20' | PORTIONS: 4

SEABASS FILLET in parchment paper with celery, capers and cherry tomatoes

Cook: Panagiotis Siafakas.

Species: Seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*).

INGREDIENTS

- 4 seabass, divided into fillets (we ask the fishmonger to fillet them)
- 3 tender stalks of celery, chopped
- 8-10 cherry tomatoes, cut in half
- 1 tsp. of caper soup, salted
- 2 spring onions, chopped
- 60 ml olive oil
- salt, freshly ground pepper

METHOD

To prepare the seabass fillet on the baking sheet with celery, capers and cherry tomatoes, preheat the oven to 200°C. On a smooth surface, spread 2 large sheets of greaseproof paper, one on top of the other, and arrange the fillets on them.

Season them with salt and pepper and oil them well.

Scatter the celery, cherry tomatoes, capers and green onions and close the parchment paper.

Arrange in a pan and bake for about 20 minutes.

Take out of the oven, carefully open the parchment paper so as not to get burned by the steam and pour the fillets with the herbs on a plate.

Sprinkle with the delicious juices of the parchment paper and serve.

The European seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) is a particularly vulnerable species to fishing during its spawning period. Furthermore, this species is the most widely farmed species in the Mediterranean.

MARINATED SEA BREAM ON PUMPKIN PURÉE

Cook: Nena Laura Mazoy/Ana G Cabado
City, Country: Chenlo, Pontevedra, Spain.
Species: Sea bream (*Sparus aurata*).

INGREDIENTS

MASH PUMPKIN

- 1 onion
- 1 carrot
- 1 red and 1 green pepper
- 1 big tomato
- 1 skimmed yogurt
- 1 large pumpkin
- 1 avocado
- 3 cloves of garlic
- 3 tablespoons of homemade tomato sauce
- Salt, EVOO

FISH

- 2 big sea bream fillets
- Half glass Ribeiro (white) wine
- Juice of half a lemon
- Parsley
- Onion powder
- 1 clove of garlic
- EVOO, paprika, salt

METHOD

PUMPKIN PURÉE

Cut the ingredients.
Poach onion, garlic and peppers.
Add carrot and tomato.

Add the pumpkin, cut in pieces.
Leave on low heat for 35/40 min.
Stir from time to time.

Let cool and add the avocado and yogurt.
Blend well with the blender.

MARINATED SEA BREAM

Fillet and cut into pieces.
Prepare the marinade with the lemon, wine, parsley, salt, pepper, onion and crushed garlic.
Add the fish and leave it in the refrigerator for 1 hour.
Strain and fry in EVOO.
Put on kitchen paper.

The European seabream (*Sparus aurata*), commonly known as the gilt-head bream, has a robust, oval body with a distinct golden stripe between its eyes. It inhabits rocky or sandy bottoms in coastal waters, primarily in the Mediterranean Sea, the Black Sea, and the eastern Atlantic. Due to the lack of scientific data on its stock status captured seabream should be consumed with moderation. Choose line-caught or sustainably farmed seabream.

PREPARATION: 15' | COOKING: 20' | PORTIONS: 4

BAKED SEA BREAM WITH ROASTED POTATOES

Cook: Lazarina Dimitrova, homemade at Sofia, Bulgaria.

Species: Sea bream (*Sparus aurata*).

INGREDIENTS

- 4 seabreams, cleaned
- 2 lemons
- 1 kg potatoes
- 4 tbsp olive oil
- 2 cloves of garlic
- Fresh rosemary
- Fresh thyme
- Salt
- Pepper

METHOD

Preheat the oven to 180°C.

Put a list of baking paper over the tray.

Wash the fish and pat it dry, then cut half of each so that you would be able to spice them inside.

Cut the lemons into thin rounds.

Rub salt into the fish inside and out.

Drizzle with olive oil and sprinkle pepper inside the fish.

Peel the garlic clove and cut into thin slices. Place them inside the fish. Add lemon slices in each fish, leaving 1-2 for the top.

Separate the thyme leaves, and together with the rosemary sprigs, place them inside the fish.

Peel the potatoes and cut them into large pieces.

Place them in the tray around the fish. Season with salt and pepper and drizzle with olive oil. Peel and chop the garlic cloves, spread the pieces over the potatoes. Put some rosemary between the potatoes.

Bake the fish and potatoes in the preheated oven for 25-30 minutes or until done.

The gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*) is recognizable by the golden band on its forehead, located between the eyes, which resembles the shape of a crown. It is also marked by a black spot at the beginning of the lateral line. Its sides are silver-gray in color and have an oval shape.

PREPARATION: 15' | COOKING: 30' | PORTIONS: 4

SEA BREAM ON A "LAYER" OF VEGETABLES

Cook: Chef Dina Nikolaou.

Species: Seabream (*Sparus aurata*).

INGREDIENTS

- 4 breams whole cleaned
- 1 small pumpkin
- 1 large, sweet potato, peeled and cut into medium pieces
- 3 carrots, peeled and cut into medium pieces
- 1 red onion, cut into medium pieces
- 20 cherry tomatoes
- 1 clove garlic, chopped
- 300 ml white wine
- 100 ml olive oil
- 80 gr. butter
- 2-3 sprigs of fresh marjoram
- 2 tsp. sweet fennel seeds
- Juice of 2 lemons
- Salt & pepper

METHOD

Preheat the oven to 200°C with air. Clean the pumpkin, cut it into small pieces, season with salt and pepper and sprinkle with a little olive oil. Spread the pumpkin, the sweet potato and the carrots on a baking sheet lined with non-stick paper and bake for 15 minutes.

Season the fish with salt and pepper and sprinkle them with the juice of 1 lemon. Take the sheet out of the oven, spread the onion, garlic and cherry tomatoes. Lay the fish, score a little on their skin in 2-3 places and scatter the marjoram and fennel seeds. Sprinkle with the wine, the remaining olive oil and the juice from the second lemon. Return the sheet to the oven and continue baking for 25-30 minutes. Halfway through the baking time, open the oven and use a spoon to sprinkle the fish, with a little of the liquid from the pan, spread the butter over the fish and continue baking until they are soft.

PREPARATION: 30' | COOKING: 15' | PORTIONS: 4

SEA BREAM IN THE OVEN WITH A CARROT CRUST

Cook: chef Nena Ismirnoglou.

INGREDIENTS

- 4 sea breams, about 450-500 g. each, cleaned
- 1 lemon cup

FOR THE MARINADE

- 2 tsp. soup mustard, Dijon type
- 3 tsp. tablespoon lemon juice
- 7 strands of Kozani saffron
- 1 carrot, coarsely grated
- 1 tsp. sweet orange zest
- zest of 1 small lemon
- 1 clove of garlic
- salt, freshly ground pepper

METHOD

To prepare the bream with carrot crust in the oven, rub the fish with the lemon wedge and salt.

In a small pot, boil the grated carrot with the Kozani saffron in 1/2 cup of water, for about 10 minutes or until soft.

Let it cool a little and beat it in the Food processor with the rest of the marinade ingredients.

Preheat the oven to 200°C.

Coat the sea bream well with the thick marinade and place them in a pan that can fit them exactly.

Bake for about 15 minutes or until done but not dry.

The gillthead **sea bream** (*Sparus aurata*), like all sparid species, is a hermaphroditic animal that undergoes sex change during its life cycle. It initially develops as a male and later transforms into a female. This biological trait makes the sparid species particularly sensitive to fishing pressure.

PREPARATION: 20' | COOKING: 25' | PORTIONS: 4

SEA BREAM IN THE OVEN WITH VEGETABLES AND HERBS

Cook: chef Niki Chrysanthidou.

Species: Sea bream (*Sparus aurata*).

INGREDIENTS

- 4 sea breams (about 250 - 300 g each), cleaned
- 2 carrots (preferably organic), thinly sliced
- 2 potatoes (preferably organic), thinly sliced
- 1 broccoli (the florets), washed
- 2 stalks of celery with its leaves, chopped
- 4 - 5 sprigs of chopped parsley (leaves only)
- 2 cloves of garlic, sliced
- 2 bay leaves
- 1 tsp. dry sweet thyme
- 4 tsp. olive oil soup
- juice of 1 lemon
- salt, pepper
- 1 wine glass white, dry wine

METHOD

To make bream in the oven with vegetables and herbs, first wash and cut the vegetables.

Preheat the oven to 180°C.

Lightly oil a baking pan or ovenproof dish.

Place the sea bream and between them the carrots, potatoes, broccoli, garlic cloves, celery, parsley and bay leaves.

In a bowl, beat the olive oil with the thyme, lemon, salt, pepper and wine.

Pour the mixture over the breams and bake them in the oven for 20 - 25 minutes.

PREPARATION: 15' | COOKING: 5' | PORTIONS: 4

GRANCEOLA DO

By the Italian restaurant Mori Venice Bar, Paris .

A restaurant committed to the preservation of marine resources, signatory of the Ethic Ocean charter.

Species: Spider crab (*Maja brachydactyla* in Atlantic or *Maja squinado* in Mediterranean sea).

INGREDIENTS

- 4 spider crabs or 240 g of spider crab meat
- 150 g of lettuce heart and chicory
- 100 g of raw celery
- Extra virgin olive oil
- Zest and juice of orange and lemon to taste
- 1 fresh or dehydrated orange, depending on the season
- Seasonal fruits (redcurrants, etc.)
- Chives
- Salt and pepper

METHOD

Shell the spider crabs, collect the meat, and season it with olive oil, citrus zest and juice, chives, salt, and pepper.

Place the seasoned crab meat inside its cleaned and emptied carapace (or any other hollow container).

Top with julienned lettuce heart and chicory.

Garnish with celery «tagliatelle» previously soaked in ice water.

Add two thin slices of fresh or dehydrated orange, depending on the season, or other fruits.

Enjoy your meal!

“ *The Mori Venice Bar restaurant has suspended its brown crab-based recipes for several months due to the overexploitation of this species. It has replaced it on the menu with spider crab, a species currently very abundant in the Atlantic. Shelled by the restaurant team or delivered pre-shelled by a young Breton company, spider crab meat is highly appreciated by the restaurant's guests.* ”

”

The spider crab is easily identified by its spiny, triangular carapace and long, thin legs. Its body color varies from reddish-brown to yellowish. Found in rocky and sandy seabeds at depths of up to 150 meters, it inhabits the Atlantic Ocean and the Mediterranean Sea. This slow-moving scavenger is highly valued for its delicate, flavorful meat.

PREPARATION: 15' | COOKING: 5' | PORTIONS: 4

LANGOUSTINE SALAD

Cook: Natacha Morin, at home.

Species: Langoustine (*Nephrops norvegicus*).

INGREDIENTS

- 200 g of cooked langoustines
- 200 g of firm-flesh potatoes
- 10 radishes
- ½ head of lettuce (or lamb's lettuce or spinach)
- ¼ pink onion (or red onion)
- 4 pickles
- 1 carrot
- Parsley
- Sesame or pumpkin seeds
- Rapeseed oil
- Walnut vinegar
- Mustard

METHOD

POTATOES

Cook the potatoes en robe des champs (unpeeled, whole, in salted water). Ideally, cook them the day before so they are well chilled.

SALAD AND GARNISH

Wash the lettuce.

Slice the radishes and pickles into rounds.

Thinly slice the raw onion.

Peel the carrot, then continue peeling to create thin ribbons.

Chop the parsley.

Dice the cooled potatoes.

VINAIGRETTE

Prepare a classic vinaigrette with 2/3 oil, 1/3 vinegar, and mustard to taste.

PLATING

Arrange all the ingredients in a large serving dish. Drizzle with the vinaigrette and sprinkle with sesame or pumpkin seeds before serving.

The Norway lobster, also known as langoustine, has an elongated body covered in a hard, orange-pink shell, with long, slender claws. It inhabits burrows in muddy seabeds at depths of 20 to 800 meters in the Northeast Atlantic and the Mediterranean Sea. This nocturnal crustacean is prized for its tender, sweet meat. Preferably choose langoustines from sustainable populations, caught using traps.

BLUE CRAB AND CUTTLEFISH RICE

Cook: Joan Capilla Pepiol.

Restaurant: L'Algadir del Delta.

Species: Blue crab (*Callinectes sapidus*) and cuttlefish (*Sepia officinalis*).

TIP: The sofrito (lightly fried onions, garlic, red pepper, and, in this case, cuttlefish) serves as the base for Spanish-style rice dishes.

Joan Capilla is a Catalan chef renowned for his commitment to sustainability and local gastronomy. In 2007, at the age of 25, he founded L'Algadir del Delta in Poble Nou del Delta, Tarragona, Spain, a hotel and restaurant that reflects his passion for local cuisine and sustainability. His focus on sustainability is reflected in practices such as using local produce in his restaurant and reducing the consumption of supplies.

INGREDIENTS

Cuttlefish Sofrito

- 2 cuttlefish (approx. 200 g each)
- 50 ml olive oil
- 200 g onion (finely chopped)
- 2 cloves of garlic (minced)
- 1/2 teaspoon sweet paprika
- 150 g crushed tomato
- 1 teaspoon ñora pepper pulp
- 4 strands of saffron
- 1 bay leaf

Blue Crab Stock

- 25 ml olive oil
- 3 large blue crabs
- 1500 ml fish stock

For the Rice

- 200 g Carnaroli rice from the Ebro Delta (or any risotto rice)
- 2 tablespoons minced garlic and parsley
- 2 tablespoons chopped almonds, dried bread, etc.
- 2 tablespoons cuttlefish sofrito (from the recipe above)
- Approx. 1300 ml blue crab stock with crab pieces
- Sea salt (INFOSA salt from the Ebro Delta if available)

METHOD

Cuttlefish Sofrito

Cut the cuttlefish into 1 cm squares. Heat the olive oil in a pan and cook the onion until golden brown. Add the cuttlefish and garlic, cooking for a few minutes. Stir in the crushed tomato, sweet paprika, and ñora pepper pulp, and cook briefly. Finally, add the saffron strands and bay leaf. Set the sofrito aside.

Blue Crab Stock

Clean the blue crabs by removing the shell from the head, cleaning the bellies, and dividing each crab into two pieces. Heat olive oil in a large pan and sauté the crabs until golden (use this same pan later for the rice). Transfer the sautéed crabs to a casserole with the fish stock. Cook for at least 30 minutes to infuse the stock with the crab's flavor.

Rice

In the casserole dish where the crabs were cooked, add the cuttlefish sofrito and rice. Stir to combine. Add the minced garlic and parsley to blend the flavors. Heat the rice and then pour in the blue crab stock. Turn the heat to maximum. Stir well for the first few minutes, then add the salt and chopped nuts. Cook the rice on high heat for 10–14 minutes, depending on your heat source. Around minute 6, adjust the salt if needed. Between minutes 8 and 12, check the rice's texture (this may vary based on water quality, stock pH, atmospheric pressure, or heat type).

Let the rice rest for a few minutes before serving.

The blue crab (*Callinectes sapidus*) originally from the East Coast of the United States, is now an invasive species found in the Mediterranean. This crustacean can grow up to 20 cm wide. It is highly aggressive and omnivorous, making it a serious threat to local ecosystems. It endangers native species by competing for food and space. Its presence also affects fishing activities, as it damages nets and devours catches. The blue crab highlights the complex challenges posed by invasive species. It is valued for its meat and is beginning to be appreciated in cuisine.

PREPARATION: 15' | COOKING: 10' | PORTIONS: 4

STEAMED MUSSELS

Cook: Marc Magrans.

Species: Mussels (*Mytilus Galloprovincialis*).

INGREDIENTS

- 1 kg of mussels
- 2- garlic cloves
- 1 bay leaf
- Enough olive oil to cover the base of the pot
- Pepper to taste

METHOD

Clean all the mussels by removing the filaments attached to the shells. Discard any open, as this might indicate that the mussel is dead. To ensure freshness, it's recommended that you check the capture date when purchasing.

Once you have all the mussels cleaned and ready, heat a saucepan with the oil, garlic, and bay leaf. When the oil is hot, add the mussels and let them cook for approximately 8 minutes. Move the saucepan every 2/3 minutes to ensure even cooking.

The mussels will release the water that will help them cook.

Be careful not to add salt. You can add some pepper, but it's enough with the salty water the mussels release.

Once 8 minutes have passed, check that all the mussels are open and turn off the heat. Serve and eat immediately.

PRESENTATION

Place the mussels in a large bowl, and spoon some of the remaining broth into a small bowl to be used as a dipping sauce for the mussels.

Sustainable Note about Delta de l'Ebre mussels:

These mussels are aquaculture products grown in a marine protected area and biosphere reserve. They are produced in an environmentally respectful manner and comply with all EU legal requirements.

PREPARATION: 15' | COOKING: 10' | PORTIONS: 4

MUSSELS BURGAS STYLE

Cook: Ana Hristova, Bulgaria.

Species: Mussel (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*).

INGREDIENTS

- 2 kg mussels
- 300 - 400 g rice
- 1 onion
- 2 carrots
- 3 tomatoes
- 100 - 150 ml white wine
- 2 bay leaves
- Mint
- Oil, 1 lemon, salt and black pepper to taste
- Dill and parsley

METHOD

First, clean the mussels. Remove the broken and open ones. Place them in a deep saucepan, pour water to cover them. Stir vigorously, then discard the water. Repeat rinsing until the last water discarded is clean. Place the mussels in a colander to drain.

Sauté the finely chopped carrots and onions.

Pour in hot water and the rice. As soon as the rice starts to cook, add the mussels (with the shells). Season with white wine, bay leaves, mint, and salt and pepper – all spices to taste.

Cut the tomatoes into cubes and add them to the pot 5 minutes before the end of cooking. Gradually, all the mussels will open when cooked. They will be ready at about the same time when the rice is cooked through - in about 15 minutes.

Finely chop the dill and parsley and sprinkle over the dish. Slice the lemon and decorate the dish.

Serve immediately.

The mussel (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) is a bivalve mollusk with a smooth, elongated shell that is typically dark blue or black in color, with a slightly iridescent sheen. It is commonly cultivated in coastal areas, where it filters plankton and other nutrients from the water. Preferably choose farmed mussels from well-managed and sustainable aquaculture systems.

PREPARATION: 15' | COOKING: 40' | PORTIONS: 4

CONFIT OCTOPUS

Cook: Chef Nuno Batista.

Species: Common octopus (*Octopus vulgaris*).

INGREDIENTS

- 2 kg Frozen octopus tentacles
- 500 ml olive oil
- 5 rosemary stems
- 5 cloves of garlic
- 4 bay leaves
- 200 g onions
- 500 g ginger chopped
- 20 g butter
- 1 liter red wine
- 300 g black grapes halved
- 2 heads pak choi
- 1,5 kg washed potatoes
- Salt
- Butter
- Herb oil

METHOD

OCTOPUS

Defrost the octopus. Wash and place it on an oven dish. Pour olive oil over the octopus, add half of the rosemary, two smashed cloves of garlic, chopped onion and bay leaves. Cover with foil and bake in the oven at 160°C about 2 hours.

POTATOES

Heat a pan, add 1 tbslp of olive oil and gently fry 3 cloves of chopped garlic. Cut the potatoes into chunks (with the skin on) and place in a deep tray. Season with salt, bay leaves and rosemary and pour on the garlic olive oil. Bake in the oven for 30 minutes, drain.

PAK CHOI

In a pan, gently fry the ginger in butter until lightly golden. Add the wine and bring to a gentle boil. Blanch and fresh the grapes and skin. Cut the pak choi in half and poach for service, drain.

PRESENTATION

Place the potatoes in the centre of the plate. Arrange the octopus and pak choi. Garnish with the black grapes and drizzle with herb oil.

The common octopus (*Octopus vulgaris*) has a large, massive head and a broad mantle that protects the stylet (a remnant of its shell) and connects its arms (tentacles). It has eight tentacles, each longer than its mantle, and covered with more than 200 suckers. This benthic, demersal species lives on rocky and sandy substrates, hunting for food close to the coast in temperate and tropical waters worldwide, typically at depths of up to 100 meters. The common octopus has a short life cycle, with females dying shortly after laying their eggs, a process known as «senescence.»

PREPARATION: 10' | COOKING: 70' | PORTIONS: 4

POLVO À LAGAREIRO

Cook: Chef Carlos Lopes Maciel.

Species: Common octopus (*Octopus vulgaris*).

INGREDIENTS

- 1 kg whole octopus
- 500g baby potatoes
- 5 garlic cloves (peeled)
- 1 bay leaves
- Flat leaf parsley
- Salt
- 250 ml olive oil

METHOD

BABY POTATOES

Preheat the oven to 160°C. Wash the potatoes well. Put them in a baking dish with plenty of coarse salt, cover with aluminum foil and bake for about 50 minutes until soft. Once cooked remove from the oven.

OCTOPUS

Bring a large pot of water to the boil, add the octopus, cook for 30 minutes approximately. Skewer a tentacle to check that the texture is firm but not tough. Remove from heat and allow to cool in the cooking liquor. After 15 minutes remove the octopus. Separate the head from the tentacles. Add the octopus tentacles to the potatoes, season with some coarse salt. Add the garlic cloves, parsley leaves, bay leaves, and cover with the olive oil. Increase the temperature of the oven to 210°C, roast for 20 minutes until golden brown.

PRESENTATION

Serve in the basking dish to retain heat.

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